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Urban Health Challenges: An Analysis of Population-Environment, Nexus in Douala, Cameroon

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Abstract

This study aims at investigating the relationship between the rising population and the immediate living environment in relation to their impact on health in Douala, Cameroon. Douala is a rapidly growing metropolitan city with a population exceeding 4 million and an annual growth rate of over 3.44%. Douala faces significant challenges related to the provision of basic urban services, particularly in marginalized neighbourhoods. In order to investigate these, the research employs the Urban Health Framework to explore how the city's social and physical environments are influenced by local health outcomes. A mixed survey research was adopted for this study and the study population comprised all the 120 neighbourhoods that make up the Douala metropolis. A random sampling technique was used to collect field data from these 120 neighbourhoods. Data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. These data was used to identify common health challenges such as malaria, typhoid, dysentery, and cholera, which are exacerbated by poor water quality, inadequate sanitation, and substandard housing. Primary data was sourced from questionnaires and interviews while secondary data was gotten from reviewing hospital records. The study results showed a high prevalence of malaria compared to the other infectious diseases with variations between environmental factors like water pollution, stagnant water bodies, poor housing and the prevalence of these diseases within most of the marginalized neighbourhoods. This therefore emphasize the need for improved urban planning and health interventions to achieve targeted goals. The findings further reveals the importance of more sensitization on environmental sanitation at individual levels and the need for multi-level collaboration between international organisations, national and municipal governments, and civil society to enhance urban health and wellbeing in Douala especially in marginalized neighbourhoods.

KEYWORDS: Urban Health, Health Challenges, Population Environment, Population-Environment nexus, Douala, Cameroon

1. Introduction

The urban population has been growing at unprecedented rates with huge economic, social and environmental impacts (UN-HABITAT, 2023). These urbanization rates, according to Snow (2024) have been growing rapidly within the past century. This current growth, and as

projected by the United Nations Population Bureau, two of every three people globally will be living in urban or semi-urban areas by 2050. This therefore implies the need for more housing, more jobs, and more space, which is linked to land use dynamics among others that have to cater for the rising urban population (Fombe et al., 2001).

In recent studies on urban development, the economic, social and environmental factors are being considered as very important for the wellbeing of the urban population (Rowe et al., 2003). It is no doubt why contemporary cities focus on these indicators as a way forward to modern cities that are inclusive, equitable and sustainable (UN-HABITAT, 2023). However, with the growing urbanization trends, city authorities are faced with challenges of providing basic facilities needed to maintain the social, economic and environmental balance of the city (Fombe et al., 2012). Studies by Sop et al. (2020) proves that our environment defines our health, and growing situations of expanding cities automatically leads to increased health challenges such as pollution, inequitable access to health services, especially physical infrastructure. Ndjama et al., (2008) argued that the future of human development depends on creating healthier urban environments. As the old adage goes, "health is wealth". Therefore, for urban areas to develop, the urban population needs to stay healthy.

The World Health Organisation defines health as a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of diseases or infirmity. A number of studies have been carried out to link health and development, one of which is the works of Madhiwalla (2007) who pointed out that improving the state of health contributes to the realization of other developmental objectives such as economic development, labour productivity growth, responsiveness to innovations and future orientations. Meier et al. (2008) opined that, the relationship between health and development is a reciprocal one. To them, economic and environmental development tends to improve health status, while better health contributes to economic and environmental development.

Statistics from the United Nations World Urbanisation Prospects (April, 2024) shows that the population of Douala stands at 4,203,108 inhabitants with an annual growth rate of 3.44% and a growth of 139,908 inhabitants from last year. With such growth rate, the state of wellbeing of the inhabitants needs to be checked in order to achieve the inclusive and sustainable urbanization objective as explained in Target 3 of Sustainable Development Goal 11 by 2030. However, the situation is not the case in Douala as the rising urbanization has led to untold environmental and social consequences to the Douala residents. The urbanization pattern in Douala is not closely monitored by urban authorities leading to occupation of marginal lands in some neighbourhoods by the urban poor, pollution of water bodies, consumption of unsafe drinking water, rising urban poverty and poor access to urban facilities like health, employment and affordable education. Examples of such neighbourhoods include Bonassama, Bojongo, Youpwe, Yassa, New Airport, as well as Koto and Bangwe among others. These neighbourhoods are prone to floods that constantly destroy properties and death of humans. In addition, most of the water bodies within the Douala metropolis have dark colours with pungent smells, indicating high levels of pollution from nearby industries and households.

Furthermore, with the sedimentary composition of the Douala Basin, seepage of pollutants and sea water incursion characterizes the constant source of pollution of underground water bodies that makes it unfit for domestic uses. This situation, according to Lambi (2001), Fogwe (2005) and Fombe (2006) has been the major cause of water borne diseases in Douala added to the poor situation of stagnant water bodies. As a backdrop from these, the current study is set to investigate the challenges of urban health as a link to environmental, social and economic wellbeing of the inhabitants of Douala metropolis.

2. The Urban Health Framework

The Urban Health framework was designed by Vlahov et al. (2006, 2007) and argued that the social and physical environment that defines the urban context are shaped by multiple factors and multiple players at multiple levels. They added that global trends, national and local governments, civil society, markets and private sectors all shape the context in which local factors operate. Governance interventions in the urban setting must consider national and municipal determinants and should strive to influence both the urban living and working environments as well as intermediary processes that include social processes and health knowledge. Furthermore, this framework assumes that the urban environment in its broadest sense (physical, social, economic and political) affects all strata of residents, either directly or indirectly. It should be pointed out that interventions can also influence the key global, national and municipal drivers as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: The Urban Health Framework
Source: Culled from Vlahov et al., (2006, 2007)

As deduced from Figure 1, achieving urban health can only be through global, national and local collaborations. In the case of Douala, all these levels are seen. This was especially illustrated through collaboration during the Covid-19 period as Douala is an entry point into the country. The presence of UN-HABITAT, GIZ, WHO, Goal 3 of the Sustainable Development Goals, among other international organisations working on health in Cameroon and Douala in particular provides the needed understanding on the role played by international collaborators on health situations in the country. Added to this, there exist national laws guiding health care provision as well as municipal laws on health care and sanitation with the urban environment. Furthermore, being a cosmopolitan environment, the urban health is reflected in all dimensions and its influence on residents is highly determined by the physical environment, social class, economic influence and political drive of the city authorities.

3. Materials and Methods

Study Area

Douala, a metropolitan city and the economic capital of Cameroon, is located between latitude $3^{\circ} 2'$ and $4^{\circ} 2'$ N of the equator and longitude $9^{\circ} 42'$ and $10^{\circ} 75'E$ of the Greenwich Meridian. The city constitutes part of the vast coastal basin that extends from the Mount Cameroon Region to the southern part of Kribi with the low mangrove shore made of fluvio-marine Quaternary alluviums bordering its south-western flanks as indicated in Map 1, Douala is bordered to the south by the Atlantic Ocean, to the west by Dibombari, to the east by Edea and to the north by Nkam Division ((BOUPDA, 1994).

Map 1: Layout of Douala metropolis indicating its different neighbourhoods
Source: Adapted from N.I.C. Administrative Map (1999)

Douala is a tropical city engulfing the River Wouri estuary; a terrain of sandy, low-lying landscape dissected by several tributaries and small streams. According to Guy (1986), cited in Fombe (2005), the city covers a built-up area of approximately 850 km² and developing into two separate sections. There is the main town (Douala Town) located on the left bank (eastern section) of the River Wouri and a secondary town, the Hickory Town (present day Bonaberi) located on the right bank (western section) of the same river. The Douala metropolis has been divided into six administrative units: Douala I to VI for convenience of administration and it has more than 120 neighbourhoods which covered an estimated surface area of 16,000 hectares in 2000 (BOUPDA, 1994).

The demographic structure of the population of Douala is much diversified in origin and predominantly youthful in character. The population is composed mainly of the active age group with the youthful category of 15-34 years who are mostly immigrants (Fombe, 2005). The youthful population in 2002 represented 39%, while those of the working age group represented 53% and the aged 7.1% (National Institute of Statistics (NIS, 2003). The sex ratio of the population favours the male population with a ratio of 10:8, thereby explaining the high rate of migration and the dominance of retail activities within the Douala metropolis. This demographic composition of Douala has not changed significantly as the youthful population still makes up a majority of the population. Added to the immigration rates, it has increased due to the ongoing crisis within the Anglophone regions that has seen a surge of Internally Displaced Persons from the south west and northwest regions into the city. However, this population has been stable for some time as the intensity of the crisis has reduced significantly.

Douala is a cosmopolitan city and constitutes a major economic hub of the country. The city is the economic capital of Cameroon and harbours over 70% of the country's industrial sector. The urban economic sector is very vibrant resulting from the dynamic and enterprising character of the business population. The economy of Douala encompasses both the informal and formal sectors preoccupying more than 90% of the active population (Fombe, 2005).

Methodology

This study adopted the survey and analytical research techniques. Also, the sample size of this study comprised the entire 120 neighbourhoods that make the Douala Metropolis. To be able to cover the entire neighbourhood, a random sampling technique was adopted. This helped to save time and reduce bias. Data collected included both the primary and secondary sources. Secondary sources of data comprised of both published and unpublished materials. Some of the secondary sources include outpatient statistics from some selected health institutions like the Douala General Hospital, the Laquintinie Hospital, Muna's Clinic, Saint Ange Medical Centre, Bambini Medical Centre (especially for pediatric cases), the Baptist Health Centre, the Vitale Medical Centre and the Kerthan Clinic. Information collected provided the frequency of occurrence of particular illnesses related to environmental factors. To obtain the above information from these health institutions, a clearance was collected from the Delegation of Public Health. This clearance was closely monitored by the General Supervisor of the various institutions. For ethical consideration, patients' names were not provided. Also, published

sources from the UNHABITAT, GIZ, Public Health Ministry and authors were consulted. Information gathered helped to provide indebt material on Douala and cases related to urban environmental health in other cities.

Primary sources on the other hand constituted direct interviews to some administrative staffs like the Regional Chief of Centre for Health and Sanitation of the different councils in Douala, the Chief of Centre for the National Water Corporation (SNEC) and coordinators for health in GIZ and Association for Community Awareness, Douala. Questionnaires were also used to collect primary data. The questionnaires were distributed to inhabitants of Douala using a systematic sampling technique. Furthermore, water sources, their quality and availability were examined. Inferential statistics were used to depict water quality and possible causes of pollution. Aesthetic parameters adopted for this study included water colour, taste and smell. This was done especially for water sources like boreholes, streams and wells. In addition, dumpsites, their conditions and proximity to residential areas were determined with use of a GPS and photographs taken.

Data collected were analysed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. The content analysis was used specifically to analyse data collected from health institutions. Plates were used to present dumpsites and their proximity to residential areas and water sources. For the quantitative analysis techniques, tables were developed from field questionnaires and presented by use of pie charts, histograms, bar graphs and line graphs.

4. Results

Common health challenges within cities are viewed from environmental factors to factors that include work stress and other related causes. In Douala, Field data (2023) shows that common illnesses based on their frequency of occurrence include Malaria, Typhoid, Dysentery, Cholera, Diarrhea, Hypertension and others (like cold, flood related stress and work stress). Their frequency of occurrence is as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Proportion of Common Illnesses in Douala based on Frequency of occurrence
Source: Outpatient Department of some selected Hospitals, Douala (2023)

Malaria prevalence was highest and noted to exist in all neighbourhoods though it varies from one neighbourhood to another. This can be related directly to the environmental factors of poor drainage or marshy environments, bushy surroundings and slow moving streams that are heavily polluted with domestic wastes. Plate 1 illustrates examples of a poor drainage (left) and the bushy environment (right) that encourages mosquito breeding within the Ndobbo Neighbourhood of Douala.

Plate 1: Poor environmental conditions in the Ndobbo Neighbourhood of Douala
Source: Field work (2023)

Also, a correlation between neighbourhood and health was established. From this, it was realized that, malaria, cholera (exception of Douala I), Typhoid, Dysentery, Hypertension, Diarrhea and other illnesses like common cold, exists in all parts of Douala. Being a tropical city, the climate poses as an enhancing factor for the breeding of mosquitoes. Dysentery on the other hand was found to exist in all neighbourhoods. This can be attributed to the water quality the population depends on as the CDE water supply remains unreliable. The rates are highest in Douala VI and IV, followed by II and V, III and I in that order as shown in Figure 3. This is directly related to water supply where the inhabitants of Douala IV and VI depend mostly on wells and boreholes than the CDE water supply. The lack of appropriate treatment of these water sources before consumption can be looked upon as the dominant cause of typhoid and dysentery within the population.

Fig. 3: Variation of Illnesses in the different Douala Municipalities
Source: Field data (2023)

In comparing the situation of housing and health, it was realized that the housing type has a direct correlation with the type of disease prevalent in the area. Areas of sub-standard housing are dominated by illnesses like malaria, cholera, typhoid, dysentery and diarrhea while those of standard are more of malaria and hypertension. Though the others still exist within these standard housing units, their intensities are far below those within the sub-standard housing units. In neighbourhoods like Mabanda, Youpwe, Tergal, New Town Airport, Bonaloka and Madagascar among other similar neighbourhoods, housing conditions and environment play an immediate role with respect to health hazards in the neighbourhoods. Plate 2 illustrates examples of such conditions that act as a way of enhancing poor health conditions within the neighbourhoods. Plate 2 shows the close proximity of miondo production besides a well illustrating a high possibility of seepage and direct contamination into the well. Also, within most neighbourhoods of poor housing, toilets are directly drained along gutters. This situation plays a huge role in creating a pungent smell within the neighbourhood and possible airbourne

diseases within Douala. Plate 3 shows a similar situation within the Mabanda Neighbourhood of Douala. It is no doubt that the rate of malaria and cholera within Douala IV has been recurrent within the last ten years or more.

Plate 2: Miondo production besides a well water used for other domestic purposes in Newbell
Source: Fieldwork (2023)

Plate 3: Drainage systems from pit toilets connected to gutters as way of disposal
Source: Field work (2023)

The study further examined the relationship between water supply and health in Douala. Water supply in Douala remains the sole responsibility of the Water distribution corporation (“La Camerounaise des Eaux” (CDE) that distributes water to most quarters of the Douala municipality. Based on water supply, the population relies on four major sources (springs, boreholes, wells and CDE). The use of these sources, however, varies from one community to

another. For example, boreholes have become more popular for the supply of portable water as water from CDE became unreliable. Quarters like Newtown-Airport, Bonamoussadi and Bepanda depends almost entirely on boreholes while others like Brazaville, Ndofo, Mabanda and Yassa depends more on wells than the CDE.

In other neighbourhoods like Bonamoussadi especially, water supply remains scarce. Some water stands go for days without water and the communities are forced to depend on wells, springs and boreholes depending on which is readily available. Field work proves that in most instances, the borehole and wells have remained reliable and therefore constitute one of the basic sources of water supply to most neighbourhoods. Plate 4 shows water cans and buckets of inhabitants waiting for water from a single outlet pipe provided by Aquavita in the Bonamoussadi neighbourhood of Douala.

Plate 4: Bonamoussadi residents lining up to fetch water provided by the Aquavita Company
Source: Field work (2023)

Besides the supply of water in Douala, its quality has remained doubtful. Most stream sources have been polluted as colour, odour and aesthetics have been heavily altered as seen in Plate 5. The porous nature of the Douala basin creates a favourable environment for pollution through seepage from septic tanks, open dumps and industrial effluence among others. Inferential data (2013) on microbial analysis in Douala shows that all water samples tested in Douala (except those in Ndogbong and Bepanda) have presence of total coliform. This illustrated that contamination was mainly from anthropogenic sources of pollution. Based on this, Table 1 illustrates the potential pollution sources and suspected pollutants within the Douala metropolis.

Table 1: Pollution sources and their suspected origin

Pollution Sources	Suspected Origin
Dump sites (waste sorting sites and HYSACAM spots)	Leachate, hazardous pollutants (from Batteries), heavy metals (mercury, lead), organics
Welding workshops	Oil, metallic particles, paints
Garages (painting, cars and moto bikes)	Lubricants, hydrocarbons, paints, grease
Open dumps	Leachate, hazardous pollutants (from Batteries), heavy metals (mercury, lead)
Oil sales points	Oil, hydrocarbons
Septic pipes in to drainage pattern	Sewage (effluent and sludge)
Industries (waste in to rivers)	Industrial effluents (e.g Guinness)
Fridge repair shops	CFC, oil
Poor drainage system	Effluent, sewage, sludge
Farming activities	Seepage of fertilizers
Dumping of plastics	Complete coverage of water bodies
Dumping of Construction materials	Cement and other carbonates

Source: Modified from Akenji (2013)

Plate 5: Polluted streams exhibiting dark colouration as evidence of pollution

Source: Field work (2022)

Field evidence also proves that, only 17% of the total respondents in Douala use the nearby streams within their neighbourhoods for domestic purposes like washing, flushing of toilets, cleaning, and mainly for building construction. The remaining 83% argue that the streams have been rendered unfit for any human use. They depend more on boreholes and wells for water

supply as the CDE supply is unreliable. Such polluted streams remain potential breeding grounds for mosquitoes, cholera, typhoid and other related illnesses within such neighbourhoods.

Furthermore, the dumping of waste close to neighbourhoods was another major factor affecting the health of residents within the municipality. Most residents dump waste along the roads as seen in Plate 6, or in cases where trash cans are being provided, collection takes a very long time leading to spillage of waste around the surrounding as seen in Plate 7.

Plate 6: Waste dumped along the streets in the Mabanda Neighbourhood
Source: Field work (2023)

Plate 7: Over spilled Trash Can within the Mabanda Neighbourhood
Source: Field work (2023)

On the other hand, disposal of effluence from households remains a problem in some neighbourhoods. A good example is in the Mabanda neighbourhood, Ndobo neighbourhood as well as Youpwe, Bonamoussadi and Newtown Airport neighbourhoods. In most of these

neighbourhoods, makeshift structures are erected and high tides are used as a way of disposing the waste as illustrated in Plate 8. Such disposal procedure illustrates a potential cause of cholera within such neighbourhoods.

(a)

(b)

Plate 8a illustrate a structure used as a toilet in the Ndobo neighbourhood before high tides and (b) shows the structure during high tides

Source: Field work (2023)

Discussions

Cities sit at the centre of modern life and acts as engines that drive the wider society and their ability to generate wealth and opportunities that shapes our health. According to the United Nations, over 70% of the world's population will live in cities. However, this increase in urban size is also marked by an unequal distribution of assets- human, financial and environment – can be considerable, leading to vastly different health outcomes for residents depending on income, gender, culture and ethnicity. Field evidence has been able to provide these differences ranging from the housing differences and health, neighbourhood and health, environment and health as well as water quality, waste disposal and health.

Findings in this study show that there exist a number of recurrent illnesses within the Douala municipality. These illnesses range from Malaria, Typhoid, Cholera, Diarrhoea and hypertension. These recurrent illnesses are directly linked to the different environments related to the economic, social and environment. It can be deduced from the findings here that, illnesses like hypertension is more common in Douala I than in the other neighbourhoods while cholera is almost not existing in Douala I. However, malaria, being a tropical illness exist in all the municipalities but more recurrent in the Douala IV, V and VI which are highly prone to floods and characterised by stagnant water. This finding is similar to that of Harpham (2009) who identified a number of recurrent illnesses within Sub-Saharan African cities. To him, malaria, respiratory illnesses and diarrhea remain the most outstanding and are directly linked to the environmental conditions of the living environment. Also, findings linked to housing and health was examined. Findings proved that, there is a direct correlation between housing

standards and health: disease proliferation is more within neighbourhoods of low housing standards compared to areas of high housing standards. This finding is similar to the works of Fombe et al., (2014) during their study on housing and disease nexus in Buea and Agbortoko (2018) on urban environmental management in Douala. The studies show a direct link of increasing disease prevalence in poor standard houses compared to high standard housing neighbourhoods.

In addition, findings on water supply and water quality show the high rate of pollution of the existing water bodies in Douala. These water bodies have been rendered unfit for both human consumption and agricultural activities. This finding is similar to that of Singh et al., (2022) who attributed challenges of water supply and pollution to the changing land use patterns within the urban environment. To them, the different types of pollutants produced from the different land uses including the discharge of untreated industrial effluents and indiscriminate dumping of waste are major contributors to water pollution in cities and this severely affects the health of urban residents.

5. Conclusion

The study on population-environment nexus in Douala reveals that there are significant urban health challenges faced by the different neighbourhoods. As the population of Douala continues to increase, so too are the challenges resulting to pollution, sanitation challenges, water scarcity as well as access to healthcare systems. These environmental factors have direct impact on the health and wellbeing of the urban population of Douala. Addressing these urban health challenges in Douala requires a multifaceted approach that considers both the population and the environment. Strategies such as improving access to clean water and sanitation facilities, promoting sustainable urban planning and enhancing healthcare services can help mitigate the negative impacts of urbanisation on health. Also, raising awareness about the importance of environmental conservation and public health can empower communities to take action towards creating a healthier urban environment. It is on this premise that this work concludes that the population-environment nexus in Douala highlights the complex interplay between urbanisation, environmental degradation and public health. By implementing targeted interventions and fostering collaboration between stakeholders, it is possible to address these challenges and create a healthier and more sustainable urban environment for the residents of Douala.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following as way forward to improve the population-environment nexus of Douala:

- There is need to improve upon the creation of data-led initiatives. This will assist in generating specific health and population data, explore them to identify and build an accurate picture of health issues and then target interventions where they are most needed

- Addressing the root cause of health challenges like waste disposal, water accessibility, job creation and improved sanitation within the urban space of Douala. This will help reduce their intended consequences
- There is the need for the central government to effectively devolve powers to local councils especially in the areas of health and sanitation decisions. This will allow locals to have a say on the decision of investing in the health sector.
- There is need to encourage CDE - CAMWATER to increase production as they have been trying to do. However, this should not be limited to the affluent zones but to all neighbourhoods in need of water supply. In the same light, sensitisation of experts from this body together with health experts can mobilise to sensitise the public on water treatment especially boreholes to avoid risk of water borne diseases.
- There is need to encourage sensitization on waste disposal by the waste management company in Douala (HYSACAM). This will reduce the indiscriminate dumping of waste within the neighbourhoods and roads as well as improve upon the responsibility attached to waste disposal through coordination between HYSACAM and residents on days of evacuation.

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